

MEDICAL SCIENCES

THE CONDITION OF THE GASTRIC MUCOSA IN PATIENTS WITH PEPTIC ULCER WITH HYPERTENSION AND DIABETES TYPE 2, PHARMACOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF AIR

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Abstract

The article highlights the basic pharmacological properties of air. Since the peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum, especially with the combination of diabetes and hypertension, reduces the secretion of the protective layer of mucus in the stomach, so the use of this plant will increase the eradication effect in treatment.

Keywords: ulcer, diabetes, hypertension, air.

Introduction. Peptic ulcer (PV) of the stomach and duodenum (duodenum) is one of the most common diseases of the digestive system. Over the last three decades, views on the etiology and pathogenesis of this disease have changed significantly [1,3].

At present, the main cause of PV is infection of the gastric mucosa and DPK *Helicobacter pylori* (HP) [3], the increased virulence of which is determined by the genes of Caga, Vas, Baba, Icea [5]. The presence of an association between infection with toxigenic (CAGA+, VACA+) HP strains, the severity of chronic gastroduodenal pathology and an increase in cardiovascular risk [4] led to a study of mechanisms of exposure to this infection on the course of atherosclerosis [5,6].

The risk of HP infection increases with type 2 diabetes, as hyperglycemia contributes to the development of HP infection, the effect of chronic inflammation, homeostasis of leptin and ghrelin and insulin secretion can lead to enhancement Type 2 (CD2) [7].

HP-associated PV of the stomach and duodenum is often accompanied by disorders of quantitative and qualitative composition of the gut microbiota [6], which, in turn, play a role in the development of obesity, diabetes [1], hypertension [2], dyslipidemia and atherosclerosis.]

The purpose of the study is to investigate the phytotherapeutic effect of air in the peptic gastric ulcer combined with arterial hypertension and diabetes type 2.

Research methods. As a result of screening, 120 patients with HP-associated PVS and DPK aged 18 to 75 years (an average of $48.81 \pm 1,42$) were involved in the study. 67 patients with concomitant hypertension (hypertension) and diabetes type 2 (CD2). Among the sick men were 70 (58.3%), women - 50 (41.7%). The control group consisted of 30 practically healthy persons (PCOs) (men - 22, women - 8) in which no acute and chronic diseases were detected at the time of examination of acute and chronic diseases. We also selected 24 patients with chronic non-atrophic gastritis (HNAG) associated with HR, incl. 11 patients with concomitant hypertension and CD2 (men -12 (50%), women -12 (50%)).

All patients were in hospital treatment in the gastroenterology department of the Chernivtsi Regional

Clinical Hospital and Chernivtsi Regional Endocrinology Center in 2013-2016.

The presence of PVS and DPK was verified on the basis of a clinical picture, anamnesis data, objective methods of examination of the patient, the results of endoscopic and morphological studies of SOS and DPK.

Determination of the stage and degree of hypertension (AH) was carried out in accordance with the criteria recommended in 2013 by the European Society for Hypertension (ESH) / European Society of Cardiologists (ESC). Diagnosis of CD 2 was made according to the WHO standards 2006/2011 (HBA1C > 6.5 %, plasma glucose ≥ 7.0 mmol/l, postprandial glycemia after 2 hours ≥ 11.0 mmol/l).

Diagnosis was carried out in accordance with the national recommendations of the unified clinical protocol of primary, emergency and secondary (specialized) medical care to patients with PVS and DPK in adults, approved by the order of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine No. 613 of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine dated 03.09.2014; Unified clinical protocol of primary, emergency and secondary (specialized) medical care to patients with hypertension, approved by the order of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine No. 384, dated 24.05.2012 and recommendations of the European Society of Cardiology (European of Hypertension) and ECETY. ology - ESC) (2013); Unified Protocol "On Approval and Implementation of Medical and Technological Documents on Standardization of Medical Aid in type 2 diabetes" Order of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine No. 1118 of 21.12.2012.

Criteria for inclusion in the study: male and female patients over 18 years of age with verified peptic gastric ulcer and duodenum associated with toxigenic (CAGA, VACA) strains of *H.pylori*, including combined with arterial hypertension, I-I-I-I-II. Stage II, diabetes 2 of mild and moderate severity, subcompensated and compensated.

To verify the diagnosis of Khnag, PV of the stomach and DPK, fibrogastroduodenoscopy was performed using the GIF Q-40 apparatus Olympus (Japan) with a target biopsy according to the conventional method. Characteristics of endoscopic changes of the gastric and duodenum mucosa were carried out with the use of minimal standard terminology. Inflammatory and

atrophic changes were evaluated by degrees: 0 - absence of signs, 1 - minimum degree, 2 - moderate and 3 - pronounced.

Diagnosis of HP was performed using a rapid urease test with biopsy material, production of polymerase chain reaction (PCR) with biopsy and urease respiratory test using the Helik test system with indicator tubes ("AMA"). *Helicobacter pylori* DNA was isolated from the antral stomach biopsies using special DNA sets ("Litich". Russia). CAGA and VACA *Helicobacter Pylori* were determined by biopsy with the help of Helikopol reagents. The intensity of the signal in the gel was determined by the following criteria: weak signal (+), moderate signal (++) , strong signal (+++). The results with a weak, moderate and strong signal were taken into development. The evaluation of the detection of

H.pylori CAGA and VACA genes and their alleles was carried out according to the instructions, namely the presence of a DNA fragment of the CAGA 404 DNA. light filter and VACA (allele S1+S2, M1, M2) for 259 pcs. +286 PN, 290 p. and 352 p. in accordance.

The level of glycemia was investigated by the glucose oxidase method using standard kits of reagents of production of NPP "Philisit Diagnosis" (Ukraine). Glycosylated hemoglobin (HBA1C) was determined using a photocolometric method using a set of reagents of Spinelab (Kharkiv, Ukraine).

Research results. On the basis of the color of hematoxylin and eosin drugs, other morphometric indicators of the SOS are obtained, the data of which are given in Tables 1-2

Table 1
Morphometric indicators of the mucous membrane in patients with peptic gastric ulcer without concomitant pathology, M±m

Indicators	cagA+vacA+ n=17	cagA+ або vacA+ n=13
Enterocyte desquamation (points: 0 to 5)	3,1±0,04	2,1±0,04 p<0,05
The percentage of vessels with phenomena of stasis and (or) Suppress erythrocytes (%)	34,0±1,8	12,0±0,7 p<0,05
Stroma edema (points: 0 to 5)	2,4±0,07	1,2±0,03 p<0,05
Hemorrhage in stroma (points: 0 to 5)	1,8±0,04	1,3±0,03 p<0,05
The degree of infiltration of PMAL (points: 0 to 5)	3,1±0,08	1,1±0,02 p<0,05

Note. P <0.05 - the reliability of differences between these groups.

Table 2
Morphometric parameters of the mucous membrane in patients with peptic gastric ulcer in combination with arterial hypertension and diabetes type 2 diabetes, M±m

Indicators	cagA+vacA+ n=13	cagA+ або vacA+n=21
Enterocyte desquamation (points: 0 to 5)	3,8±0,05	2,6±0,02 p<0,05
The percentage of vessels with phenomena of stasis and (or) Suppress erythrocytes (%)	39,0±1,8	12,0±0,4 p<0,05
Stroma edema (points: 0 to 5)	3,5±0,07	1,6±0,04 p<0,05
Hemorrhage in stroma (points: 0 to 5)	2,5±0,04	1,9±0,03 p<0,05
The degree of infiltration of PMAL (points: 0 to 5)	4,1±0,08	3,5±0,02 p<0,05

Note. P <0.05 - the reliability of differences between these groups.

In general, the analysis of these tables allows you to conclude that CAGA+ VACA+ Patients are worse than CAGA+ or VACA+ patients. This is especially evident in the manifestations of inflammatory reactions, which are evaluated not only by the level of inflammatory infiltration by polymorphonuclear leukocytes (PMAAL), but also taking into account such phenomena of exudation as edema of stroma, blood stasis and erythrocyte, hemorrhage. The level of desquamation of the cover epithelium indicated the level of alternation (damage) of these cells. In patients with peptic ulcer with hypertension and CD2, damage to the SES by separate indicators was more pronounced.

Air has a lot of healing properties.

- The rhizomes include from 1.5 to 3% of essential oil.

- present
- A pinen,
- Acorin,
- aromatic compounds,
- Organic acids,
- Ascorbic acid,
- Choline,
- tannins,
- starch,
- iodine,
- resins,
- Azarildehyde,
- Vitamins B and C.

The main components are

- Caphedne,
- Borneol,
- camphor,
- Seskviterpen.

The leaves contain many tannins and essential oils. Decoction of this plant can be taken for the treatment of stomach pain.

The roots have an action that increases appetite, perfectly improves digestion, enhances the reflex separation of all gastric juice. Today, marsh marsh is used in folk medicine as a good remedy for the treatment of peptic ulcer.

Pharmacological action. *Due to these substances in the composition of the roots of marshmallows, they stimulate metabolism, normalize the digestive processes and production of secretory liquids. Vitamin C in the composition of vegetable raw materials provides nutrition to the body's cells, has a positive effect on the tone and ability of the body to withstand infectious and viral disease, the negative effects of the environment. In addition to the ability to strengthen the immunity, the root of the tortoise stimulates the work of neurons, because it contains vitamin B4. The component has a soothing and neuroprotective effect on the body. Palmitic acid, which is part of the roots, eliminates inflammation and has wound healing properties. The plant also has a bacteriostatic effect.*

Conclusion. *Given the condition of the gastric mucosa, combined with arterial hypertension and diabetes type 2 diabetes and the healing properties of the air can be said that AIR should be used in the treatment of this pathology.*

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